

Mathematical description of relativity without use of time

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1. Abstract

The smallest physically available range of distance is a quantum of distance, i.e. the so called: “Planck length” (Diplicher et al. 1995 [1]; Mohr et al. 2008 - [3]; Saslow 1998 - [4]) which will be assumed in the paper as a measure of changes. It is assumed that Planck length is the basic element (quant) of linear dimension (ie, length, distance, etc.). Space on a scale comparable to size of Planck length is grainy, quantized.

This leads to developing fundamental relationship valid in the Special Theory of Relativity, without use of the concept of time and speed. The time and speed are unnecessary. It can be assumed that there is only the concept of change, rather than the concept of time. Introduction quantum distance solves the problem of reducing the object length when it is equal to the Planck length. This is shown at the end of this paper.

Keywords: relativity; time dilation; length contraction; Planck.

2. Relativity of event's number

Let us assume that there is a source of light emitting rays in all directions and located in a train which moves along the platform. An observer standing on the platform carries out the following experiment. He calculates N quanta of the distance made by the light ray receding from the platform while the train moved to k quanta distance. For the observer the light ray moved from the source by the distance equal to $(N - k)$ quanta in the direction coincident with the movement of the train and $(N + k)$ quanta in the opposite direction. In each case, this means that when the train moves along the platform, the number of the changes in the train is different from the number of the changes on the platform. Accordingly, a question arises whether the number of the changes is bigger, in the train or on the platform. First and foremost we should realize that the number of the changes must be equal in all parts of the train. The proportionality of N towards $(N - k)$ as well as towards $(N + k)$

($N = \alpha(N - k)$; $(N + k) = \beta N$; $\alpha > 1$; $\beta > 1$) leads to the following relation:

$\alpha \frac{N - k}{N} = \beta \frac{N}{N + k}$. This means that $N = \sqrt{\frac{\alpha}{\beta}} \sqrt{(N^2 - k^2)}$. Hence, it may be concluded that

from the observer's point of view - N changes occurring on the platform correspond to $\sqrt{(N^2 - k^2)}$ changes occurring in the train moving along the platform. Because $N > \sqrt{(N^2 - k^2)}$, the observer situated outside the train concludes that the number of the changes in the platform is bigger than the number of the changes in the moving train.

As the two systems (the train and the platform) are mutually symmetrical (none is privileged), the observer located inside the train will conclude that the platform is in motion and the number of the changes in the train is bigger than the number of the changes on the platform.

Let us assume that there is a ruler in the train the distance of which we want to measure.

The measuring manner is assumed to be a number of N quanta to be traveled by the ray along the ruler. It follows that its length at rest (when the train is standing on the platform)

is $l_o = N$ quanta. Furthermore, let us assume that the train and the ruler move along the

platform and that the ruler is located parallel to the moving direction. As already mentioned,

from the external observer's point of view, a certain number of the changes on the platform

corresponds to a smaller number of the changes in the moving train. Accordingly, from the

observer's point of view- if the ruler on the platform was measured in N quanta steps, in the

moving train it will be measured in $\sqrt{N^2 - k^2}$ quanta. So, the external observer concludes

that the length of the ruler measured in the train is $l = \sqrt{N^2 - k^2}$ quanta, which, in

combination with the length at rest leads to relation $l = l_o \frac{\sqrt{N^2 - k^2}}{N}$. For the observer

located on the platform the length of the ruler in the moving train is smaller than the length of the same ruler at rest in relation to the platform.

At this point we may introduce the concept of time as a measure of changes. Thus, let us define Δt_o as the passage of time on the platform, whereas Δt will denote the passage of

time in the moving train. Accordingly, we derive relations: $\Delta t_o = \frac{1}{c} N$, $\Delta t = \frac{1}{c} \sqrt{N^2 - k^2}$,

where $\frac{1}{c}$ is the proportionality coefficient related to the movement of light (c shall denote the

velocity of light). From such simple relations the following equation follows:

$\frac{\Delta t}{\Delta t_o} = \frac{\sqrt{N^2 - k^2}}{N}$. So, the external observer may conclude that there is a different measure in the moving train and that the passage of time in the train is shorter than the passage of time on the platform.

In our experiment the number of N changes of the light moving along the platform corresponds to k changes of the moving train. Accordingly, if for the observer located on the platform the measure of the light ray displacement of N quanta is the time interval $\Delta t_o = \frac{1}{c}N$, the measure of the displacement of the train of k quanta is the same range $\Delta t_o = \frac{1}{v}k$, where $\frac{1}{v}$ is the proportionality coefficient related to the movement of the train along the platform (v shall denote the velocity of the train moving along the platform). It follows from the two relations that $\frac{N}{k} = \frac{c}{v}$. By substituting this relation in the previously

discussed equations we arrive at $\Delta t = \Delta t_o \sqrt{1 - \left(\frac{v}{c}\right)^2}$ (time dilation (Einstein 1907- [2];

Reinhardt *et al.* 2007 [5])) and $l = l_o \sqrt{1 - \left(\frac{v}{c}\right)^2}$ (length contraction (Woodhouse 2003 - [6]; Terrell 1959 [7]; Penrose 1959 - [4])).

To issues still remain two clarify. Firstly, why in the discussed experiment was it not merely assumed that $k=1$? Such approach would be erroneous, as the relation $\frac{k}{N}$ may be any positive rational number smaller than 1. Let us assume as an example that this relation is $\frac{5}{6}$.

Then, the mathematical sequence in the successive steps is the following: $\left(\frac{1}{1.2}\right), \left(\frac{2}{2.4}\right),$

$\left(\frac{3}{3.6}\right), \left(\frac{4}{4.8}\right), \left(\frac{5}{6.0}\right)$ etc. As the quanta steps may be only integral numbers, the real

sequence is: $\left(\frac{k}{N}\right) = \left(\frac{1}{1}\right), \left(\frac{2}{2}\right), \left(\frac{3}{3}\right), \left(\frac{4}{4}\right), \left(\frac{5}{6}\right)$ etc. The external observer will therefore

conclude that there are no changes in the moving train in the first step of the experiment, and, using the concept of time, the observer will state that time does not pass in the train.

The second issue concerns the measurement of objects length when they are exactly equal to Planck length. Let us assume that the object is moving at nearly the speed of light,

and the task of an external observer is measuring its length. According to the Special Theory of Relativity the length should be shortened to size smaller than the Planck length. Therefore there is a conflict between the concept of the Planck length, and the Special Theory of Relativity. The method presented in this paper solves this problem.

The physical object having a non-zero mass at rest, maybe move relative to an external observer, at most of about $k = N - 1$ quantum steps ($k = N$ means that the object moves like light). This means that - from the point of view of an external observer - the length of such an object is measured in increments of $\sqrt{N^2 - k^2} = \sqrt{2N - 1}$ quantum steps. Relativistic length equal to $l = l_o \frac{\sqrt{2N - 1}}{N}$. If, therefore, an object at rest, has a length equal to the Planck length (equal to one quantum step - $N = 1$), so when moving it has the Planck length as well.

Relativistic length equal to length of rest and is $l = l_o \frac{\sqrt{2N - 1}}{N} = l_o$.

3. References

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